

Post-experiment survey for eye-tracking participants (Aasis)

Thank you for participation! Now please answer background information questions and give feedback!

1. Your research ID (e.g. 123)

Your background information

2. Gender

3. Age

4. What is your first language? If you feel that you have more than one first language, please mention which languages.

5. Which other languages can you speak in such a way that you can use them to cope with everyday situations?

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali

- Dari
- English
- Spanish
- Italian
- Chinese
- Kurdish
- Nepalese
- Portuguese
- Polish
- French
- Romanian
- German
- Somali
- Finnish
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Hungarian
- Urdu
- Russian
- Vietnamese
- Estonian
- Other, please specify
- Swedish

6. Self-assessment of my level in spoken production in Finnish (see descriptions below)

- A1
- A2

- B1
- B2
- C1
- C2

Spoken production, level descriptions (CEFR self-assessment grids)

A1: I can use simple phrases and sentences to describe where I live and people I know.

A2: I can use a series of phrases and sentences to describe in simple terms my family and other people, living conditions, my educational background and my present or most recent job.

B1: I can connect phrases in a simple way in order to describe experiences and events, my dreams, hopes and ambitions. I can briefly give reasons and explanations for opinions and plans. I can narrate a story or relate the plot of a book or film and describe my reactions

B2: I can present clear, detailed descriptions on a wide range of subjects related to my field of interest. I can explain a viewpoint on a topical issue giving the advantages and disadvantages of various options.

C1: I can present clear, detailed descriptions of complex subjects integrating sub-themes, developing particular points and rounding off with an appropriate conclusion.

C2: I can present a clear, smoothly-flowing description or argument in a style appropriate to the context and with an effective logical structure which helps the recipient to notice and remember significant points.

7. Self-assessment of my level in spoken interaction in Finnish (see descriptions below)

- A1
- A2
- B1
- B2
- C1
- C2

Spoken interaction, level descriptions (CEFR self-assessment grids)

A1: I can interact in a simple way provided the other person is prepared to repeat or rephrase things at a slower rate of speech and help me formulate what I'm trying to say. I can ask and answer simple questions in areas of immediate need or on very familiar topics.

A2: I can communicate in simple and routine tasks requiring a simple and direct exchange of information on familiar topics and activities. I can handle very short social exchanges, even though I can't usually understand enough to keep the conversation going myself.

B1: I can deal with most situations likely to arise whilst travelling in an area where the language is spoken. I can enter unprepared into conversation on topics that are familiar, of personal interest or pertinent to everyday life (e.g. family, hobbies, work, travel and current events).

B2: I can interact with a degree of fluency and spontaneity that makes regular interaction with native speakers quite possible. I can take an active part in discussion in familiar contexts, accounting for and sustaining my views.

C1: I can express myself fluently and spontaneously without much obvious searching for expressions. I can use language flexibly and effectively for social and professional purposes. I can formulate ideas and opinions with precision and relate my contribution skilfully to those of other speakers.

C2: I can take part effortlessly in any conversation or discussion and have a good familiarity with idiomatic expressions and colloquialisms. I can express myself fluently and convey finer shades of meaning precisely. If I do have a problem I can backtrack and restructure around the difficulty so smoothly that other people are hardly aware of it.

Views on the experiment

8. What did you think about the dialogue speaking tasks (A island, B mobile phones, C furniture) used in this study?

9. How comfortable did you feel during the data collection?

- 1 Very uncomfortable
- 2 Somewhat uncomfortable
- 3 Neutral
- 4 Somewhat comfortable
- 5 Very comfortable

10. How pleasant do you think the conversation was?

- 1 Very unpleasant
- 2 Somewhat unpleasant
- 3 Neutral
- 4 Somewhat pleasant
- 5 Very pleasant

11. Please comment on the pleasantness of the conversation. (You can consider factors such as: ease of communication, friendliness or comfort level during the conversation, and any other aspects that made the conversation more or less pleasant.)

Views on the materials used during the speaking tasks

12. Do you think that the materials (pictures or toys) used during the speaking tasks were useful?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

13. If you answered "Yes" to the last question, please order the following items based on how useful you perceived the material during the speaking task. (1 is most useful, 3 is least useful. If you want to write further comments about this question, please do so in the open field in question 18.)

Pictures of equipment (The pictures in the Island task)	Select ▼
Real objects (The toys in the Furniture task)	Select ▼
Pictures of phones (The pictures in the Mobile phone task)	Select ▼

14. Do you think that the materials (pictures or toys) in the tasks helped you express yourself during the task? In what ways? (Please first choose one of the options and then write your answer in the text box.)

Yes

No

Not sure

15. When you and your partner focused on the pictures or toys together, did you find this helpful for the interaction? In what ways? (Please first choose one of the options and then write your answer in the text box.)

Yes

No

Not sure

Views on the technical side of the data collection

16. How did you feel wearing the eye-tracking glasses?

17. Did you encounter any technical problems?

18. Here you can complete your answers or give feedback

Submit